

SOME COMMENTS ABOUT DISCOURSE DEIXIS IN LITERARY TEXT (IN THE MATERIALS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

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Abstract:

This article is about the role of deixis in linguistics, emphasizing its relevance in intertextual expression and the structure of discourse. Deixis focuses on the speaker's position in time and space, anchoring communication to a specific context and shaping how meaning is conveyed and interpreted. The text highlights the relationship between social deixis and text, which encompasses communication between speakers or writers and their audiences, stressing the dynamic, context-dependent nature of language.

Key words: discourse deixis, demonstrative pronouns, spatial and temporal proximity, deictic center, discourse contexts, deictic expressions, English, Uzbek.

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In contemporary linguistics, the process of deixis is scientifically researched by various linguists and serves as an impetus for opening new aspects of scientific research on the characteristics of intertextual expression of deixis types. At the center of the system of deixis is the speech author, that is, we call a speaker and his location in space and time remains the starting point. Deixis determines the location of the speaker in a certain space during speech activity. Speaking from this point of view, deixis should be studied at the level of discourse and can be recognized as a “special case of reference” [Hanks., 1992:46]. Discourse is associated with a specific part of language, usually larger than a sentence. Discourse is mainly seen in the interaction between speakers or between writers and readers [Sylvia., Edmund, 1998:118]. Any social interaction or expression that involves language can be considered as a discourse [O’Grady W., Archibald J., Katamba F., 2011:629].

A similar definition can be found in the work of another linguist Ch. Fillmore. The scientist includes in the group of deictics “lexical and grammatical units that meaning is determined in the structure of the sentence in which they are used” and emphasizes that this sentence is “related to the text of a certain social situation” [Fillmore, 1975:75]. Ch. Fillmore suggests distinguishing four types of deixis (space, time, social relation, text deixis). Social deixis consists of forms of respect, text (discourse) deixis is a system of indications and references to other parts of the text.

The function of demonstrative pronouns *this/these*, *that/those* in speech activity is based on the principle of proximity/distance of the deictic center. In fact, this principle underlies the detailed classification of demonstrative pronouns. Realization of the proximity category in space and time is manifested in the use of demonstrative pronouns *this/these* for objects and events. The proximity category is defined with the speaker's place. Demonstrative pronouns show the person-subject of the discourse implicitly [Safarov, 2008:178-180].

The author's attitude is reflected in how he divides the text into parts, introduces a new idea and gives a systematic using of statements. The author of the text creates the content of the transmitted information on the basis of his own interpretation and selects the linguistic material with the help of various means of demonstration, highlighting one or another

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evidence, assuming a certain pragmatic purpose. It is known that at the heart of the text lies the author's subjective attitude to objects and events, his evaluation to them. In this case, the analysis of the means of expressing reality in an artistic text, such as identifying similarities between objects, comparing them, contrasting them, introducing various repetitions, clarifications can be taken into consideration.

The function of discourse deixis is to determine the "situation" (concrete or abstract) within the events that occur in the text. Referential approach to some parts of the text indicates that the text is expressed deictically. Deictic situations used in the text are one of the most important tools for the discourse deixis in giving the co-referential situation in the text:

e.g. You see, the way they work things in Blaenelly is like this: the Company has three doctors on its list, though mind you Doctor Page is far and away the cleverest doctor of the lot. (Cronin A.J. *The Citadel*. - Moscow: Higher school publishing house, 1966. - P. 28)

Bu yil kuz seryomg'ir keldi. Bo'tana oqimlar necha bor ariqchalarni yuvib, yig'ilib qolgan xasu xazonlarni surib ketdi...(Isfandiyor. *Meni tongda uyg'oting*. -T.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1986. -B. 9.)

e.g. She was dressed severely in a simple tweed suit and low-heeled shoes. This is Madame Harcourt. (Irwin Shaw. *Bread upon the waters*. - New York: Dell publishing co., 1981. - P. 194.)

Sevguvchi odam hayotga, odamlarga ham mehr bilan qaraydi. U yovuzlikdan, makr va qabohatdan yiroq bo'ladi (Temirov H. *Generalning bevasi*. -T.:Yangi asr avlodi, 2012. - B.179.)

In English texts, the discourse deixis is often expressed by demonstratives such as this, that, and personal pronouns such as he, she, it, they, and in Uzbek language, such as and personal pronouns:

e.g. All you got to remember is that you are working for Doctor Page. That is the main thing, Doctor. (Irwin Shaw. *Bread upon the waters*. - New York: Dell publishing co., 1981. - P. 29.)

Men onamning yurak urishlarini shundoqqina eshitib yotardim. Bu men uchun rohat edi. (Isfandiyor. *Meni tongda uyg'oting*. - T.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1986. - B.7.)

In English literary texts, the definite article can also be added to the discourse deixis. Because the presence of the definite article in the text is very important for the reader. The reader will quickly learn information about who or what the events are related to through the specific article. It is known that there is no article in Uzbek. The function of the definite article in English can be given in Uzbek by demonstrative pronouns such as "that, this, this, this":

e.g. A doctor spoke to me on the phone.

Bir shifokor telefonda men bilan gaplashdi.

e.g. The doctor spoke to me on the phone.

O'sha (mazkur: THAT/THE) shifokor telefonda men bilan gaplashdi.

Demonstrative pronouns are used for almost the same purpose in both English and Uzbek languages. That is, the meaning of the demonstrative pronoun "o'sha" in Uzbek can be given by the pronoun "that" and the meaning of the pronoun "this" can be given by demonstrative pronouns such as "bu, shu". Discourse deixis is present in the text in two ways: anaphoric and cataphoric. It is known that if an action takes place or occurs during the discourse, demonstrative pronouns like that/those are used for earlier execution of events during the discourse: this/these:

e.g. Never leave home without it, like they say on television. (Irwin Shaw. *Bread upon the waters*. - New York: Dell publishing co., 1981. - P. 320.)

(anaphoric)

Kechikib bo'lsa ham hayotda odam o'z o'rnini belgilab, o'zligini tanib olishi kerak. Buni u yaxshi biladi. (Isfandiyor. Meni tongda uyg'oting. – T.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san'at nashriyoti, 1986. – B.108.) (anaphoric)

e.g. This last phrase had become a comic byword in the household. They both used it, indiscriminately, facetiously, as a clincher to all their arguments. (Cronin A.J. *The Citadel*. – Moscow: Higher school publishing house, 1966. – P. 239.) (cataphoric)

Nurbekning o'sha, uzoq judolik so'nggidagi hayajonli uchrashuv chog'ida bildirgan iqrori, birga bo'lishga astoydil ishtiyoqi xonimga g'alati ta'sir etdi (Temirov H. *Generalning bevasi*. –T.:Yangi asr avlodi, 2012. – B.342.) (cataphoric)

In conclusion, the analysis provided highlights key features of discourse deixis in English and Uzbek literary texts, emphasizing both similarities and differences. The use of demonstrative pronouns like this/these and that/those in English and their counterparts in Uzbek, such as bu, shu, and o'sha, demonstrates how deictic expressions are employed to indicate spatial and temporal proximity or distance relative to the speaker's deictic center. Additionally, the role of anaphoric and cataphoric references within discourse deixis illustrates the ways in which elements of a text are cohesively connected and how meaning is established through reference to other parts of the text.

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